

Data Platform Overview

Mission

- 01** Sustainably Funded Core Data Resources
- 02** Coordinated Ecosystem of Node Data Resources
- 03** Support European Research Community

Leadership

Ulrike Wittig
ELIXIR Germany
Platform Lead

Patrick Ruch
ELIXIR Switzerland
Platform Lead

Silvio Tosatto
ELIXIR Italy
Platform Lead

Fabio Liberante
ELIXIR Hub
Programme Manager

Gavin Farrell
ELIXIR Hub
Platform Officer

Data Platform - Tasks 2019-2023

T1: Community and data management network - Engagement

1.1 - Engaging ELIXIR communities

1.2 - Identify the sustainability framework for the
Data Management Expert Network

1.3 - Monitoring of EDP engagement with Communities with
FAIR Data Management Framework adoption maturity matrix

T2: Data Integration

2.1 - Integration of the “long tail” of data into FAIR databases

2.2 - Aggregation databases and registries

Community Network

Data Manager Network

Engaging pan-European expert network of Data Managers who connect national programmes and drive knowledge exchange within the ELIXIR Nodes

→ RDM Community

Biocuration Focus Group

Coordinate ELIXIR-ISB interactions and a venue for curators to find solutions to shared problems

Research Data Alliance FG

Engagement and alignment with RDA

Biodiversity Focus Group

Analysis of needs in literature data management

→ Biodiversity Community

Data Platform - Tasks 2019-2023

T₃: Scalable Curation

- 3.1 - Normalization of lesser studied entities in supplementary data
- 3.2 - Alerting, novelty and continuous learning for triage as a service
- 3.3 - Coordination of upcoming Implementation Study proposals in Data Platform scope**

T₄: Administration and support for Core Data Resource (CDR), Deposition Database (EDD) portfolio and Community Data Resources

- 4.1 - Leverage the interactions with the Global Biodata Coalition to support the CDR business cases to establish a sustainability strategy for the ELIXIR Data Platform resources**
- 4.2 - Monitoring of CDR landscape to identify emerging infrastructure needs and ensuring QA/QC of existing CDRs and EDDs to maintain ELIXIR standard
- 4.3 - Establish a guideline of Key Community Database identification

Scalable Curation

Credit Attribution APICURON

Biocuration databases

CDRs and smaller community repositories

New interest (e.g. FAIRsharing)

BioHackathon 2023 session to promote

IT, UK, DE, EBI

The logo for APICURON, with the word "APICURON" in a bold, dark red, sans-serif font. A small white icon of a person with arms raised is integrated into the letter "O".

Curation of Lipid Pathways by Domain Experts to Generate Open Access Biology Resources *UK, NL*

Integrating epitranscriptomic data into the ELIXIR ecosystem *IT, EBI, IL*

Scalable Curation of TF-TG interactions via Integration of NLP and VSM *NO, LU, CH*

Scalable extraction of human genetic and phenotypic data from peer-reviewed literature *UK, ES*

Core Data Resources

Fundamental importance

Broad life science community
Long-term preservation of biological data

Wide applicability & usage

Complete collections of generic value to life science
Authority in their field with respect to one or more characteristics
High levels of usage, scientific quality and service

WP3 - Scope

Biocurators make research data available to the scientific community in a structured and standardized way

- *Highly demanding and time-consuming*
- *Difficult to acknowledge and quantify*
- *Biocurators need a trusted way to showcase their work*

Biocuration - mapping resources and needs
Holinski, Burke, Morgan, McQuilton, Palagi. (2020) F1000

WP3 - APICURON

Biocurators making Contributions

APICURON

Curation platforms send curation data to APICURON

APICURON analyses the data

Updates Curator Portfolio

Award achievements

Updates ORCID profile

WP4 - APICURON

Works (1) Sort

DisProt - biocurator

Data set
 URI: <https://dev.apicuron.org/orcid/0000-0001-6859-3648#disprot> [Show less detail](#)

Description
 409 generation event
 2 revision
 558 invalidation event

Added
 2021-09-25

Last modified
 2021-09-25

Source: APICURON

1. **Agent** (Curator' ORCID)
2. **Entity** (Curated object ID → Protein, publication, ...)
3. **Activity** (Curation activity - W3C PROV classes)
 - *Generation*
 - *Revision*
 - *Invalidation*
4. **Timestamp**

WP3 objectives

- Support the **recognition** and credit **attribution** of activities which **curate, annotate** or otherwise **contribute** to the increase of data in relevant resources such as knowledge bases.

- Leverage the work of **APICURON** to provide an infrastructural component to use in **different contexts** beyond more traditional biocuration activities (e.g. knowledge bases), ranging from ELIXIR registries (e.g. **bio.tools, RDMkit, FAIR Cookbook, FAIRsharing**), to code contributions (e.g. in **GitHub**) and data management/stewardship (e.g. **data brokering**).

- The resulting service will link the mapped data citations and credits for primary contributions to **citation networks** (e.g. **OpenAIRE KG**).

- In addition to the technological component, it will explore the “sociological” implications for the “**person infrastructure**”, including career pathways, fostering adoption and user **engagement** (e.g. with **gamification** techniques).

Activity 1 - Technical developments for recognition

Plan of work

- Continuous **on-boarding** of ELIXIR data resources in APICURON
- APICURON linking relevant information from **FAIRsharing** (e.g. resource description)
- Expanding technical functionalities of APICURON based on new resources
- Annotating APICURON entries with **Bioschemas**
- Harvesting data from **GitHub**
- Visualisation of additional **statistics** for curators
- Establishing an embeddable **widget** (that people can use in their public profile pages, which links to their corresponding profile page on APICURON)

Outcome

- APICURON established as ELIXIR's service for **recognition** and **credit attribution**, with a wide range of connected data resources
- Expanded people and resource profiles providing rich statistics promoting **engagement** implemented

D3.1 - Report on resources integrated in APICURON (IT-UPD M36)

D3.2 - Demonstrator for expanded profiles providing rich statistics in APICURON (IT-UPD M30)

Activity 2 - Engagement and gamification for recognition

Plan of work

- Evaluate use cases for APICURON resources
- Landscape analysis of resources for defining granularity of tracked contributions (resource view)
- Strategies for promoting engagement and gamification (people view)
- Defining relevant statistics for recognition

Outcome

- Best practices for integrating resources into APICURON established (resource view)
- Guidelines for maximising contributor engagement by leveraging gamification principles (people view)

D3.3 - Report on engagement and gamification strategies, describing resource and people views (IT-UPD M24)

Activity 2 - Engagement and gamification for recognition

Plan of work

- Engage with ELIXIR Platforms and Communities
- Engage with STEERS, EVERSE and GraspOS
- Engage with EOSC task force on research careers

Outcome

- APICURON is recognized both within and outside ELIXIR as a relevant infrastructure service for recognition and credit attribution.

D3.4 - Report on uptake of APICURON as an infrastructure service (IT-UPD M36)

Responsibilities

WP Partnership
IT-UPD - Damiano Piovesan
SE-UPPS - Mihail Anton
UK-UCAM - Valerie Wood
CH-SIB - Patrick Ruch
FR-CNRS - Alban Gaignard
GR-ATRC - Thanasis Vergoulis
IT-UPD - Silvio Tosatto
DE-HITS - Ulrike Wittig
GR-AUTH - Christos Ouzounis
GR-AUTH - Fotis Psomopoulos
IT-UPD - Adel Bouhraoua
UK-UOXF - Allyson Lister

Milestones

- M3.1 - Bioschemas entities for APICURON defined (**FR-CNRS 15**)
- M3.2 - Prototype for harvesting GitHub contributions implemented (**SE-UPPS 24**)
- M3.3 - Use cases for APICURON evaluated (**IT-UPD 12**)
- M3.4 - Outreach link established with relevant EU Projects (e.g. STEERS, EVERSE and GraspOS) (**GR-ATRC 18**)

Deliverables

- D3.1 - Report on resources integrated in APICURON (**IT-UPD M36**)
- D3.2 - Demonstrator for expanded profiles providing rich statistics in APICURON (**IT-UPD M30**)
- D3.3 - Report on engagement and gamification strategies, describing resource and people views (**IT-UPD M24**)
- D3.4 - Report on uptake of APICURON as an infrastructure service (**IT-UPD M36**)

Partners

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